

K. E. Volkov

Financial crises: causes, consequences, and prevention options

KEYWORDS

financial crises,
causes of
economic crises,
unemployment,
market failure,
risk management,
consequences of
financial risks

ABSTRACT

Introduction. The relevance of the article lies in the fact that analyzing the effects of financial crises on the economy, finance, labor market, and social sphere enables governments and central banks to develop more informed and effective economic policies.

This article aims to examine the causes, consequences, and potential solutions to preventing financial crises.

Materials and methods. The research methodology involves the study of relevant Internet resources related to the topic, followed by synthesizing and generalizing their findings.

Results. Financial crises are an integral phase in the development of economic relations, both within individual countries and globally. The causes of financial crises can be explained through specific theoretical frameworks that take into account modern economic phenomena. Typically, crises result from the introduction of new financial instruments, methods, and management practices. To mitigate their negative impacts, an integrated approach is essential, incorporating preventive measures at both national and corporate levels.

Conclusion. The findings of this study can inform the development of methods and recommendations for preventing financial crises, tailored to current economic conditions, and can be applied in educational settings. Prospects for further research include analyzing the dynamics and specifics of financial crisis development, identifying key stages in their progression, and forecasting their occurrence in specific economic sectors.

FOR CITATION

Received: Sep 12, 2023
Accepted: Dec 17, 2023
Published: Mar 1, 2024

Volkov, K. E. (2024). Financial crises: causes, consequences, and prevention options. *Economic Consultant*, (1), 34–46. <https://doi.org/10.46224/ecoc.2024.1.3>

This is an open access article distributed under a Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike International License (CC-BY-SA 4.0) that allows others to share the work with an acknowledgement of the work's authorship and initial publication in this journal

INTRODUCTION

Financial crises pose a significant threat to the functioning of not only the financial but also other sectors of the state's economy. At the same time, the most severe consequence may be a halt in economic growth and a default of the country. Emerging innovations, new goods and services, and ways of providing them, as well as transactions and financial instruments, contribute to emerging crisis phenomena in the financial sector. In the context of globalization and integration, these phenomena can spread to several countries or affect almost the entire world. In this regard, it is essential to investigate the causes, consequences, and potential preventive measures for this phenomenon.

Today, the global economic system remains vulnerable to various shocks, including political changes, pandemics, natural disasters, and sharp fluctuations in commodity prices. Financial crises can have severe economic and social consequences, including rising unemployment, declining living standards, business bankruptcies, and the need for extensive government interventions to stabilize the situation. Studying the experience of various countries in the field of financial market regulation and crisis response helps identify the most effective strategies and tools to prevent crises and minimize their consequences.

Understanding the causes and mechanisms of financial crises helps improve the financial literacy of the population, which, in turn, can reduce crisis-related risks and strengthen individuals' ability to adapt to changing economic conditions.

LITERATURE REVIEW

B. Açıkgöz et al. write that economic crises are times of disaster when economic mistakes made by governments affect people. The authors believe the financial crises of the twentieth century revealed the impact of infection risk on the economy, acting as a hazardous virus that infects all cells of the body [1]. The authors also note that each successive crisis differed from its predecessors in terms of underlying causes and the economic conditions in which it emerged [2].

P. Pascual i Domènech wrote that a growing discrepancy between the behavior of the main economic variables and the expectations of investors and consumers causes financial crises. The variables consist of the amount of savings and the volume

of demand caused by changes in prices, wages, and interest rates. This discrepancy leads to excessive investments in a particular asset, fueled by expansion of lending, and ultimately fails to yield the expected results for investors [3].

T. Hauner argues that the empirical relationship between social inequality, aggregate wealth, and financial crises highlights the crucial role of the distribution of accumulated assets in the macro-financial stability of wealthy countries. The author concludes that countries with greater wealth inequality face greater financial instability [4].

P. Arora et al. provide empirical evidence that systemic financial crises can have a causal effect on income inequality and that vulnerable employment may be the driving mechanism [5].

A. Ari and R. Cergibozan find that income inequality leads to increased household debt, primarily in developed countries where the financial sector is more developed and interest rates are lower. According to the authors, governments should pursue appropriate tax and preferential policies to reduce income inequality, rather than using monetary policy as a temporary tool to mitigate the effects of income inequality on low- and middle-income segments of the population [6].

V. Vlachos examines the impact of macroeconomic factors on living standards during periods of macroeconomic uncertainty. The author demonstrates that the role of government spending in providing social protection and unemployment benefits is crucial in mitigating the extent of severe material deprivation. At the same time, economic growth in less industrialized economies will not contribute to reducing severe material deprivation through labor and wage channels [7].

T. C. Nguyen et al. argue that political and institutional factors, which significantly influence the duration of financial crises, do not receive sufficient attention. The authors, relying on an extensive database of 125 countries observed in 1976-2017, find that the electoral cycle, political ideology, majority governments, institutional quality, and the independence of the central bank are important factors [8].

Financial crises in different countries have unique characteristics that depend on various factors, including the country's economic structure, political conditions, the level of development of its financial markets, and its foreign economic relations.

P. Benigno et al. note that the European institutions responded promptly to the COVID-19 pandemic by implementing several policy measures. Reducing the risks of financial instability in the European Union proved insufficient due to the time horizon of centralized fiscal policy and persistent adverse shocks [9].

M. Kaakeh and K. K. Gökmenoğlu analyze the indicators of the Turkish financial crises of 1994, 2000, and 2009. The authors demonstrate that, in the current state of the Turkish economy, the primary indicators of the crisis are fundamental macroeconomic variables, including the stability of the banking sector and global economic events [10].

M. Ardan believes that Turkey experienced its most profound crisis in 1994. Financial liberalization and the liberalization of foreign trade in the subsequent period led to the fact that the Turkish economy, which was not yet ready, faced a crisis. The April 5, 1994 program of economic stability failed to prevent the emergence of new financial crises in the medium and long term, as the necessary structural reforms were not thoroughly and decisively implemented [11].

Several studies examined the causes, phenomena, and consequences of crises in the USA [12], Europe [13; 14], Italy [15], England [16; 17], Germany [18], and Latin America [19], among others.

Financial crises may have unique characteristics in each country, and their consequences may vary depending on the specific conditions and measures taken to overcome them.

Thus, it is essential to examine existing economic theories and models that explain the causes of financial crises, their mechanisms, and consequences. It is necessary to collect and analyze statistical data on financial crises in different countries and regions, including macroeconomic indicators, data on financial markets, and other variables. It is essential to develop and refine methodological tools for studying financial crises, including the creation of data collection techniques, analytical tools, and models to assess the effectiveness of crisis prevention and management measures.

Scientific research facilitates the evaluation of the effectiveness of government policies in regulating financial markets, the banking sector, and other factors affecting financial stability, while also supporting the development of recommendations for their enhancement.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The materials consisted of studies and reviews from scientific journals on economics and finance, focusing on the causes, mechanisms, and consequences of financial crises (e.g., The Journal of Economic Inequality; Open Economies

Review; Public Choice; Italian Economic Journal; Journal of Evolutionary Economics; Atlantic Economic Journal).

The following data were used: dynamics of the Moscow Exchange index (until November 27, 2017, for the MICEX index); dynamics of average house prices in the United States for the period 2007-2008; dynamics of stock prices of Lukoil and Rosneft in 2008; and capital outflow from Russia from 2008 to 2022.

Research methods include statistical, comparative, and time series analysis.

RESULTS

The effects of financial crises are most clearly seen when they are considered together with their causes. To this end, we will cite the factors most frequently mentioned by modern researchers as the origin of crisis phenomena and describe the possible consequences of their implementation in each specific case.

1. The root cause of these crises is new tools and transactions that differ radically from traditional ones. These innovations are often more complex to use and may involve irrational implementation conditions. Their adoption can lead to a decline in asset values, triggering significant market fluctuations and, ultimately, the emergence of crisis phenomena.

To assess the most realistic reflection of the crisis's impact on the Russian stock market as a whole, let us examine the dynamics of the Moscow Exchange index (see Fig. 1).

Figure 1 Dynamics of the Moscow Exchange index (until 27.11.2017 – the MICEX index) [20]

The Moscow Exchange index, a key indicator of the Russian stock market, is calculated based on the market prices of the most liquid shares of highly capitalized Russian companies in ruble terms. As shown in Figure 1, it experienced its most substantial falls in 2008-2009 and 2022. Examining the causes of various crisis periods, it is important to note that the 2008 crisis – commonly known as the Global Financial Crisis – originated in the American real estate market, particularly within the mortgage sector in the early 2000s. This was largely due to the widespread issuance of loans to borrowers with low credit ratings, unverified incomes, or minimal down payments. Moreover, to attract more customers, structured financial products such as mortgage bonds and collateralized debt obligations (CDOs) were created, allowing financial institutions to resell mortgages on the market and thereby stimulate demand for mortgages, leading to rising residential real estate prices [21].

However, over time, many of these borrowers were unable to repay their loans, which led not only to an increase in defaults and enforcement proceedings on mortgage loans, but also to a drop in residential real estate prices (see Fig. 2), thereby causing significant market fluctuations, affecting not only the real estate sector, but also other sectors of the economy. Thus, an increase in mortgage defaults led to a decrease in the value of mortgage-backed securities on the market, creating problems for banks and financial institutions that held a large number of these securities. Since banks issued loans based on the valuation of property, taking into account rising real estate prices, the fall in real estate prices led to a situation where real estate was worth less than expected, and loans turned out to be unsecured.

Figure 2 Dynamics of average house prices in the USA for the period 2007-2008, \$ [22]

Large financial institutions faced serious liquidity and solvency issues. The panicked withdrawal of capital by investors caused a sharp decline in stock and bond prices [23]. The crisis spread to financial markets worldwide, including Russia. First, the crisis reduced demand for Russian goods and raw materials, as the global economy slowed down. Russia is a major exporter of oil, gas, and other raw materials, so the decline in demand for these goods hurt the Russian economy. Second, the crisis resulted in significant losses for Russian companies and investors. Prices for oil and other commodities declined, resulting in a decrease in revenues and share prices of oil-producing companies, and causing a drop in quotations on the Russian stock market, as well as losses for investors (see Fig. 3).

Figure 3 Dynamics of stock quotations of Lukoil and Rosneft companies in 2008, RUB [24]

Moreover, the crisis in the United States caused global instability in financial markets, causing investors to withdraw their funds from developing countries, including Russia, and transfer them to more stable assets in the United States and other developed countries, which led to capital outflow from Russia (see Figure 4).

As a result, the Russian economy was severely affected by the mortgage crisis in the United States.

In addition to the oil and gas sector, the stock market in the banking sector also reacted sharply to the current situation, as external borrowings, a key component of its resource base, became more expensive.

Figure 4 Capital outflow from Russia by year: 2008-2022, in billions USD [25]

The second crisis was caused by political reasons. On February 24, 2022, following the President of the Russian Federation's announcement of a special military operation, the Moscow Exchange index declined from 2740.31 percentage points to a minimum value of 1681.55 percentage points, representing a 38.6% decrease [26]. The stock market collapse was so devastating that Russian stock exchanges suspended trading for 26 consecutive days, from February 26 to March 23, 2022. This situation was observed for the first time in the modern history of the country's stock market development. Until this year, the longest suspension of trading on the Moscow Stock Exchange had only occurred in 1998, lasting 4 days.

2. Transformations of the global economic system, which lead to global inconsistencies, are caused by the loss of stability in its functioning. For example, certain states, due to their unique development trajectories and economic orientations, experience persistent balance deficits. In contrast, others have a surplus, which leads to a shortage of resources for some and a surplus for others, ultimately resulting in financial failures.

Examples of countries with balance deficits:

- for many years, the United States has had a substantial public debt, resulting in recurring budget deficits. The reasons include heavy spending on defense, social programs, and infrastructure projects.

- Brazil is also facing a balance sheet deficit. High spending on social programs, pensions, and infrastructure projects, combined with economic challenges, can lead to an increase in debt and a government budget deficit.
- Examples of countries with a balance surplus:
- Germany is renowned for its economic strength and consistently maintains a surplus in its state balance sheet, which is partly attributed to the country's robust export sector and its fiscal policy aimed at achieving a balanced budget.
- Switzerland is also an example of a country with a balance sheet surplus. The high level of economic development, stability of the financial system, and limited spending on social programs enable the government to maintain a budget surplus. For example, the United States had an external debt of \$31.456 trillion in 2022 and \$33.792 trillion in real-time 2023, which means that the United States borrows significant amounts of money from other countries that it must repay [27]. This may lead to problems, as an increase in external debt could result in higher interest payments and limited opportunities for domestic investment. On the other hand, Switzerland is known for its balance sheet surplus; this means that it exports more goods and services than it imports – for example, in 2020, Switzerland had a trade surplus of 65 billion Swiss francs. This can result in the accumulation of currency surpluses within a country, leading to an appreciation of its national currency. Consequently, a stronger currency may pose challenges for exports by making goods and services more expensive for foreign buyers.

Both examples demonstrate how deficits and surpluses can harm the financial stability and economic development of these countries.

3. Ineffective activities of rating agencies, which in some cases neglect the standards. The most illustrative example and consequence is the mortgage crisis in the United States, when an incorrect assessment of subprime loans led to the emergence of a bubble and the collapse of the American and global markets.

4. The absence of a body that regulates and manages risk phenomena. Currently, these functions are partially implemented by the Federal Reserve System; however, this body does not have the authority to conduct supervisory actions for hedge funds, non-bank derivatives dealers, investment banks, and other similar entities.

5. Failures in the functioning of internal corporate risk management systems. Modern companies create special systems that are more focused on

assessing market and credit risk. Their main disadvantage is a standardized approach and the inability to work with complex, integrated products that are currently emerging [28].

In addition, there are various other consequences of financial crises: cessation of stable functioning of the financial sector, emergence and growth of unemployment, suspension or cessation of business activity, a decrease in payment demand, a decrease in investment activity and the flow of funds, emergence of an imbalance in foreign trade accounts. All of the above allow us to conclude that the negative impact of crisis phenomena is spreading not only to all spheres of the state's economic activity, but also to financial institutions, the population, foreign trade, industry, and other business sectors. It is worth noting that the aforementioned causes of economic crises manifest themselves at the moment of their occurrence. At the same time, the occurrence of crisis phenomena is revealed at a stage when forecasting and hedging opportunities cannot be fully used to reduce their negative impact. In this regard, anti-crisis management becomes essential, implying the development and implementation of recommendations that will allow for reducing the negative consequences of financial crises to some degree.

DISCUSSION

Notably, reducing the negative impact of both internal and external factors can make it possible to ensure Russia's financial stability most effectively in all areas of business. At the same time, changes in a particular industry have a direct impact on the emergence of vulnerabilities and threats to the entire economic system.

Summarizing all of the above, we have developed practical recommendations for leveling the crisis in Russia. To increase the effectiveness of financial crisis prevention, comprehensive work and a systematic approach are necessary. Firstly, in addition to the globally adopted directives, it is essential to create a regulator that studies and evaluates the safety of individual industries in each state. At the same time, with the development of globalization and integration, such organizations can exchange data, making it possible to take preventive measures to mitigate crisis phenomena.

Second, the methods used in the framework of the early warning system should be updated regularly, changing and adapting to innovative tools, types of transactions, and other relevant developments. In this regard, it is essential to use forecasting and evaluation techniques on a joint basis.

Third, the causes of the financial crisis, its consequences, and prerequisites, particularly the functioning of organizations and their shortcomings in activities, should be analyzed in detail to prevent a similar situation from occurring in the future.

Fourth, every organization, whether large, medium, or small, should have a specialized unit that deals with risk management, aiming to maintain the stability and transparency of the organization's functioning. Since failures in its activities can also affect the market and lead to crisis phenomena, this unit is crucial.

Therefore, several promising avenues exist for the study of financial crises. In particular, it is essential to develop more precise models and algorithms that predict financial crises by analyzing economic indicators, market trends, and other relevant factors. It is essential to examine how new financial instruments, cryptocurrencies, and digital platforms influence the emergence and spread of economic crises, and to develop effective regulatory measures to address these developments. Of considerable interest is the study of how financial crises affect the standard of living, unemployment rates, social stability, and the development of measures to alleviate these impacts.

CONCLUSION

The issues of economic development in any country are closely related to ensuring the optimal level of functioning of the state in the financial sector. By leveling or preventing crisis phenomena, it is possible to achieve the most critical indicators of the tactical and strategic development of national economies. For example, normal living conditions for the population are maintained, the necessary material and production resources are supplied to the sectors of the national economy, and the phased implementation of economic development plans is achieved by detecting and preventing negative deformations in individual elements of the system.

Financial crises are inevitable events for the economy due to the emergence of new tools, methods of conducting transactions, market participants, globalization, digitalization, and integration. They entail various adverse consequences, ranging from unemployment to a decrease and eventual cessation of economic growth within the state. Currently, there are comprehensive early warning systems that aim to predict, identify, study, and develop preventive actions to mitigate negative impact factors, thereby reducing the likelihood of a crisis. However, from our perspective, to enhance the effectiveness of this process, it is crucial to adopt an integrated approach that encompasses risk management at both the national level and within individual companies.

REFERENCES

1. Açıkgöz, B. (2023). Introduction: Models Related to the Contagion of Financial Crises. In: Açıkgöz, B. (eds) *Black Swan: Economic Crises, Volume II. Accounting, Finance, Sustainability, Governance & Fraud: Theory and Application*. Springer, Singapore. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-99-2318-2_1
2. Açıkgöz, B., & Çiloğlu, T. (2022). General Overview of Crisis Models and Financial Crises. In: Açıkgöz, B. (eds) *Black Swan: Economic Crises, Volume I. Accounting, Finance, Sustainability, Governance & Fraud: Theory and Application*. Springer, Singapore. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-19-5252-4_1
3. Pascual i Domènech, P. (2023). Economic and Financial Crises in Catalonia (1840–1914). In: Catalan Vidal, J. (eds) *Crises and Transformation in the Mediterranean World. Palgrave Studies in Economic History*. Palgrave Macmillan, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-24502-2_6
4. Hauner, T. (2020). Aggregate wealth and its distribution as determinants of financial crises. *The Journal of Economic Inequality*, 18, 319–338. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10888-020-09444-9>
5. Arora, P., Chong, A., & Srebot, C. (2023). Systemic Financial Crises and Income Inequality in OECD Countries. *Open Economies Review*, 35, 687–694. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11079-023-09741-6>
6. Ari, A., & Cergibozan, R. (2023). Income Inequality, Household Debt, and Financial Crises. In: Ari, A. (eds) *Capitalism at a Crossroads. Springer Studies in Alternative Economics*. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-23257-2_6
7. Vlachos, V. (2022). What Role for Macroeconomic Environment on Living Standards in Times of Crisis and Uncertainty? In: BEN AMEUR, H., FTITI, Z., LOUHICHI, W., PRIGENT, J.L. (eds) *Crises and Uncertainty in the Economy*. Springer, Singapore. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-19-3296-0_6
8. Nguyen, T. C., Castro, V., & Wood, J. (2022). Political economy of financial crisis duration. *Public Choice*, 192, 309–330. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11127-022-00986-2>
9. Benigno, P., Canofari, P., & Di Bartolomeo, G. et al. (2023). The Spectre of Financial Dominance in the Eurozone. *Italian Economic Journal*, 10, 59–80. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40797-023-00225-7>
10. Kaakeh, M., & Gökmenoğlu, K. K. (2022). Leading Indicators of Turkey's Financial Crises. In: Özataç, N., Gökmenoğlu, K. K., Rustamov, B. (eds) *New Dynamics in Banking and Finance. Springer Proceedings in Business and Economics*. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-93725-6_2
11. Ardan, M. (2023). 1994 Financial Crisis in Turkey. In: Açıkgöz, B. (eds) *Black Swan: Economic Crises, Volume II. Accounting, Finance, Sustainability, Governance & Fraud: Theory and Application*. Springer, Singapore. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-99-2318-2_7
12. Tori, D., Caverzasi, E., & Gallegati, M. (2023). Financial Production and the Subprime Mortgage Crisis. *Journal of Evolutionary Economics*, 33, 573–603. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00191-023-00812-y>
13. Zoega, G. (2021). Financial Crises and Current Account Surpluses. *Atlantic Economic Journal*, 49, 159–172. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11293-021-09718-1>
14. Öztürk, A. (2022). Dutch Tulip Mania: Tulip Crisis. In: Açıkgöz, B. (eds) *Black Swan: Economic Crises, Volume I. Accounting, Finance, Sustainability, Governance & Fraud: Theory and Application*. Springer, Singapore. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-19-5252-4_2
15. Arbolino, R., Boffardi, R., & Di Caro, P. (2023). Measuring and Exploring Regional Trade Resilience in Italy During Different Crises. *Italian Economic Journal*, 9, 1027–1047. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40797-023-00250-6>
16. Read, C. (2023). The Crises of 1825 and 1837. In: *Calming the Storms. Palgrave Studies in Economic History*. Palgrave Macmillan, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-11914-9_4
17. Read, C. (2023). The Fading Away of Crises After 1866. In: *Calming the Storms. Palgrave Studies in Economic History*. Palgrave Macmillan, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-11914-9_8
18. Hotori, E., Wendschlag, M., & Giddey, T. (2022). Germany: Financial Crises and Formalization of Banking Supervision. In: *Formalization of Banking Supervision*. Palgrave Macmillan, Singapore. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-16-6783-1_5
19. McKinney, S. (2021). Emerging Markets and Financial Crises. In: *An Introduction to Latin American*

- Economics*. Palgrave Macmillan, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-76617-7_9
20. *Stock Exchange Index (MICEX): 1997-2023*. Available at: <http://global-finances.ru/index-mosbirzhimmbv/> (accessed 27 November 2023).
 21. Isaev, D. V. (2020). The role of derivative financial instruments in the mortgage crisis in the USA. *Bulletin of IEAU*, 7, 5–17.
 22. *Historical US Home Prices: Monthly Median from 1953-2023*. Available at: <https://dqydj.com/historical-home-prices/> (accessed 2 September 2023).
 23. Polivalov, A. A. (2023). The mortgage crisis of 2007-2011 in the USA and the role of monetary policy in eliminating its consequences. *Economics and Management: a Scientific and practical journal*, 3, 47–60.
 24. *The leading financial portal*. Available at: <https://ru.investing.com/equities/> (accessed 2 September 2023).
 25. *Global Finance*. Available at: <http://global-finances.ru/> (accessed 2 September 2023)
 26. Timofeeva, A. A., & Guryanova, D. V. (2022). A study of the impact of financial crises on the Russian stock market. *Journal of Applied Research*, 7 (1), 32–39.
 27. *Global Finance*. URL: <http://global-finances.ru/> (accessed 2 September 2023).
 28. Kohno, P. A., & Kohno, A. P. (2021). Financial and economic crises and their mathematical assessment. *Russia: Trends and Prospects of Development*, 3, 167–172.

INFORMATION ABOUT THE AUTHOR

<p>Konstantin E. Volkov Postgraduate student. Moscow University of Finance and Law (Moscow, Russia). E-mail: v.konstant@bk.ru. ORCID ID: 0009-0008-5529-4807</p>	<p>Conceptualization, Methodology, Writing - Review & Editing, Visualization</p>
--	--

The author have declared that no competing interests exist

Copyright: © Konstantin E. Volkov, 2024

Editor: Omer Allagabo Omer Mustafa. Sudan Academy for Banking and Financial Sciences (Sudan)